

ADVANCED CONTROL STRATEGIES FOR MULBERRY MOTH (*GLYPHODES PYLAIALIS* WALKER) USING A MICRONUTRIENT SOLUTION OF ELECTROCHEMICALLY ACTIVATED WATER

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Abstract: The article discusses an innovative and eco-friendly approach to controlling the mulberry moth (*Glyphodes pylaialis* Walker), a significant pest affecting mulberry trees, using a micronutrient solution of electrochemically activated water (ECAW). ECAW, which contains reactive oxygen species like hypochlorous acid, exerts insecticidal effects by causing oxidative stress and disrupting cellular structures in the larvae. The addition of micronutrients such as zinc, copper, manganese, and boron enhances plant immune responses, improves pest resistance, and strengthens overall plant health. The method, applied primarily through foliar spraying, offers several advantages over traditional pesticides, including being non-toxic, environmentally friendly, and cost-effective, with little risk of pests developing resistance. While the method shows significant promise, further research is necessary to optimize application techniques and understand its long-term effects on agriculture.

Keywords: Mulberry moth, *Glyphodes pylaialis*, Electrochemically activated water (ECAW), Reactive oxygen species (ROS), Hypochlorous acid, Micronutrient solution, Oxidative stress, Insecticide, Sustainable pest control, Foliar spraying, Plant immune response, Eco-friendly agriculture, Integrated pest management (IPM).

Introduction

The mulberry moth (*Glyphodes pylaialis* Walker), an invasive and destructive pest, is a major concern for mulberry trees, particularly in areas where sericulture is essential for the local economy. Traditional chemical pesticides, although effective, have numerous drawbacks including the development of pest resistance, environmental degradation, and potential harm to non-target species. Consequently, alternative methods that are both environmentally safe and economically viable are in demand. One such promising method is the use of electrochemically activated water (ECAW) combined with micronutrient supplementation. This innovative approach leverages the antimicrobial and insecticidal properties of ECAW and the growth-promoting effects of essential micronutrients to control mulberry moth populations while improving overall plant health.

What is Electrochemically Activated Water (ECAW)?

ECAW is produced by electrolyzing water with a small quantity of salt, which results in the

generation of two key solutions: an anolyte (oxidizing) and catholyte (reducing). The anolyte, rich in reactive oxygen species (ROS), has been shown to possess powerful antimicrobial and insecticidal properties, making it an excellent alternative to chemical pesticides.

➤ **Key Components of Anolyte:**

- **Hypochlorous Acid (HOCl):** A highly reactive and potent oxidant that disrupts the cellular structures of pathogens and pests.
- **Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS):** Including superoxide and hydrogen peroxide, which cause oxidative stress in pests, leading to cell death.
- **Catholyte:** Primarily used to neutralize pH and enhance plant growth by providing beneficial reducing conditions, but it has limited direct pest control effects.

Figure 1. Mulberry propeller ECAW treatment process.

ECAW Mechanisms for Controlling Mulberry Moth

1. **Oxidative Stress and Larvae Mortality:** The primary mode of action for ECAW against *Glyphodes pylaialis* larvae is through oxidative damage. The reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the anolyte solution attack the larvae's soft tissues, causing membrane rupture and disruption of vital cellular processes. This results in larval death through oxidative stress mechanisms similar to those observed in other pests treated with ECAW.
2. **Membrane Disruption and Enzyme Inhibition:** Hypochlorous acid (HOCl), one of the key components of ECAW, can easily penetrate biological membranes and inactivate critical enzymes within the larvae. This leads to protein denaturation and inhibition of metabolic processes essential for larval survival and development.

3. **Reduction of Pest Habitat Suitability:** ECAW has been demonstrated to reduce the availability of suitable habitats for pests by neutralizing organic materials and microorganisms that pests often rely on. By reducing the population of these microorganisms on the plant's surface, ECAW indirectly limits the larval food supply and nesting areas, making the environment less conducive to mulberry moth proliferation.

Role of Micronutrients in Pest Control and Plant Health

Micronutrients such as zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), manganese (Mn), and boron (B) are essential for various physiological and biochemical processes within the plant. Their inclusion in the ECAW solution has several benefits, both in terms of pest control and overall plant vitality.

1. **Enhancement of Plant Immune System:** Plants require certain micronutrients to activate and sustain their immune responses. For example, zinc is involved in the synthesis of proteins that play a critical role in defense against pathogens and pests. Copper is a key element in enzymes involved in redox reactions and lignin synthesis, which strengthens plant cell walls and makes them more resistant to pest attack.
2. **Increased Production of Defensive Compounds:** Micronutrients aid in the production of phenolic compounds, phytoalexins, and other secondary metabolites that deter herbivorous pests. For instance, manganese is crucial for the functioning of enzymes involved in the synthesis of these defensive compounds. As a result, plants treated with a micronutrient solution are better equipped to produce toxins or compounds that either repel mulberry moth larvae or reduce their ability to digest the plant tissue.
3. **Improved Stress Tolerance:** When micronutrients are applied in conjunction with ECAW, plants show improved resilience to environmental stresses such as drought, high temperatures, and disease, all of which can exacerbate pest problems. A healthier plant is better able to withstand and recover from mulberry moth infestations.

Application Methods for Optimal Pest Control

1. **Foliar Spraying:** The most effective method of applying ECAW and micronutrient solutions is through foliar spraying. This allows for direct contact with the leaves, where mulberry moth larvae feed. The solution is absorbed by the plant tissues, providing systemic benefits while also acting as a contact insecticide on the surface.
2. **Soil Drenching:** In addition to foliar spraying, soil drenching with ECAW and micronutrients can enhance root health and nutrient uptake, improving overall plant vitality. Healthy roots can more effectively transport micronutrients to the leaves, further fortifying the plant's defenses.
3. **Concentration and Frequency:** The efficacy of this treatment depends on the correct concentration of ROS and micronutrients. Typically, an ECAW concentration of 100-200 ppm of active chlorine with a balanced micronutrient mixture is sufficient. Application frequency is crucial, with bi-weekly treatments during peak pest activity recommended to maintain consistent protection.

Advantages of Using ECAW and Micronutrient Solutions

1. **Non-Toxic and Environmentally Safe:** One of the biggest advantages of ECAW is its non-toxic nature. Unlike traditional chemical pesticides, ECAW breaks down into harmless substances (water and salt) after application, leaving no harmful residues on crops or in the environment. This makes it an ideal solution for sustainable agriculture.

2. **No Risk of Resistance Development:** Since ECAW operates via oxidative stress—a mechanism that directly damages cellular components—pests like the mulberry moth are less likely to develop resistance, a common issue with conventional pesticides.
3. **Cost-Effectiveness:** ECAW is relatively inexpensive to produce, requiring only water, a small amount of salt, and electricity. The combined use of micronutrients adds a slight cost but improves the overall efficacy of the solution. Given its potential to reduce pest populations and improve plant health simultaneously, this method can save farmers money by reducing the need for chemical pesticides and fertilizers.
4. **Sustainable and Organic Agriculture:** The use of ECAW aligns with organic farming principles. It is a natural, non-chemical method that helps maintain soil health and biodiversity. In many countries, ECAW has been certified for use in organic agriculture, offering farmers a valuable tool for pest control without compromising organic certification.

Figure 2. Proceedings of experiments against the mulberry moth.

Challenges and Considerations

1. **Optimal Solution Composition:** The concentration of ROS and micronutrients must be carefully balanced to avoid phytotoxicity. While ECAW is generally safe for plants,

excessively high concentrations of ROS or an imbalance of micronutrients can lead to leaf burn or nutrient toxicity.

- 2. Field Conditions and Environmental Factors:** Environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, and soil pH can influence the effectiveness of ECAW. For example, extreme temperatures can accelerate the breakdown of ROS, reducing the solution's insecticidal efficacy. Field trials are necessary to determine the best application protocols for specific regions and crop conditions.
- 3. Limited Research on Long-Term Effects:** Although ECAW and micronutrient solutions show great promise, further research is needed to explore their long-term effects on soil health, crop yield, and pest populations. Additionally, studying the interactions between ECAW and beneficial organisms like pollinators and natural pest predators is crucial for fully understanding its ecological impact.

Conclusion

The control of the mulberry moth (*Glyphodes pyralialis* Walker) using a micronutrient solution of electrochemically activated water is a groundbreaking approach in pest management. It offers a non-toxic, sustainable, and cost-effective solution to one of the major agricultural challenges faced by sericulture and mulberry crop growers. By combining the oxidative power of ECAW with the plant-strengthening properties of micronutrients, farmers can achieve effective pest control while promoting plant health and reducing environmental impact.

As more research is conducted and field trials are refined, this method has the potential to become a mainstream tool in integrated pest management (IPM) systems. With its dual action of killing pests and improving crop vitality, the ECAW-micronutrient approach aligns well with the future of eco-friendly agriculture.

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